

Designing a Roadmap for Effective and Sustainable Strategies for Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of EU Agriculture to Navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space

The EU MRLs on pesticides and EU competitiveness

Discussion paper

AUTHORS	Ana I. Sanjuán (CITA), Irene Garcés (CITA), George Philippidis (CITA)
CALL	Innovative governance, environmental observations and digital solutions in support of the Green Deal
WORK PROGRAMME Topic ID	EU agriculture within a safe and just operating space and planetary boundaries HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01-12
PROJECT WEB SITE:	https://brightspace-project.eu/

This document was produced under the terms and conditions of Grant Agreement No. 101060075 for the European Commission. It does not necessarily reflect the view of the European Union and in no way anticipates the Commission's future policy in this area.

Table of Contents

1. INTRODUCTION	3
2. METHODS.....	4
2.1. REVEALED COMPARATIVE ADVANTAGE INDEXES	4
2.1.1. REVEALED COMPETITIVE INDEX (RC)	5
2.1.2. CONTRIBUTION TO THE TRADE BALANCE INDEX (CTB)	6
2.1.3. GRAVITY BASED INDEX (Z).....	7
2.2. MRL STRINGENCY INDEX (SCORE).....	8
2.3. EMPIRICAL SPECIFICATION	9
3. DATA	10
3.1. MAXIMUM RESIDUE LIMITS.....	10
3.2. TRADE.....	12
4. RESULTS	12
4.1. DATA DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS	12
4.2. ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS	15
4.2.1. BASELINE RESULTS	15
4.2.2. RESULTS BY SECTOR AND REGION	17
5. DISCUSSION AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS	22
6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	24
7. REFERENCES	24
APPENDIX 1: THE SAMPLE	28
APPENDIX 2: ADDITIONAL RESULTS.....	31

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE 1. MRL SCORE EU VS CODEX BY HAZARD	13
FIGURE 2. HEATMAP OF THE DISTRIBUTION OF REVEALED COMPARATIVE ADVANTAGE (RC INDEX) ACROSS SECTORS AND REGIONS	15
FIGURE 3. HEATMAP OF THE DISTRIBUTION OF REVEALED COMPARATIVE ADVANTAGE (CTB VARIABLE) ACROSS SECTORS AND REGIONS	31
FIGURE 4. HEATMAP OF THE DISTRIBUTION OF REVEALED COMPARATIVE ADVANTAGE (Z VARIABLE) ACROSS SECTORS AND REGIONS	31

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE 1. CATEGORIES OF PESTICIDES BY HAZARD.....	11
TABLE 2. DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF THE RCA INDEXES.....	14
TABLE 3. BASELINE RESULTS.....	16
TABLE 4. ESTIMATION RESULTS WITH SECTOR (HS2) INTERACTIONS	19

TABLE 5. ESTIMATION RESULTS WITH REGION INTERACTIONS	21
TABLE 6. LIST OF PRODUCTS: HS6 CODES AND HS4 DESCRIPTION	28
TABLE 7. LIST OF COUNTRIES IN THE SAMPLE	30

ACRONYMS

MRLs: Maximum residue levels

EU: European Union

FAO: Food and agriculture organization of the United Nations

WHO: World Health Organisation

HS: Harmonised system. HS6: Harmonised system at the 6-digit product code level; HS2: Harmonised system at the HS2 digit level.

RCA: Revealed comparative advantage

RC: Revealed competitiveness

CTB: Contribution to the Trade Balance

Z: Gravity-based or regression-based index

1. INTRODUCTION

Within the framework of the European Green Deal, the 'Farm to Fork' and 'Biodiversity' strategies sought to facilitate climate neutrality by 2050 through a significant reduction in chemical intensive inputs. Impact assessments indicate that these strategies may diminish domestic production and trigger environmental leakage as production shifts to regions with lower standards (Barreiro-Hurlé et al., 2021; Beckman et al., 2022). To uphold fair trade and a 'level playing field' for EU producers, stakeholders advocate for 'mirror clauses' in EU free trade agreements. This mechanism ensures that imported goods comply with EU benchmarks for animal welfare, environmental sustainability, and food safety, specifically regarding pesticide residues. By utilizing a stringency index that compares EU regulation on Maximum Residue Limits (MRLs) of pesticides against the international Codex Alimentarius international baseline, this paper empirically quantifies the extent to which the EU's stringent regulatory framework, categorised by pesticide hazardousness, affects its external competitiveness and trade specialisation in the agrifood sector. There is an extensive literature showing the negative effect of stringency of MRLs adopted by importing countries on bilateral trade (Drogué and DeMaria, 2012; Ferro et al., 2015; Fiankor et al., 2021; among others), while there is some evidence in favour of the positive effects of higher standards as an export promoting tool (Maertens and Swinnen, 2009; Olper et al. 2014). This paper employs revealed comparative advantage indicators to examine the simultaneous interplay between exports and imports.

We construct a novel, product longitudinal dataset by synthesizing MRL data from two primary sources: the Eurostat pesticides and active substances database and the FAO-WHO *Codex Alimentarius* database (FAO-WHO, 2025). We collect this information at HS 6-digit level for pertaining vegetables, fruits and nuts, coffee and spices, cereals, oil seeds and cocoa. These sectors are selected due to their high regulatory pesticide intensity and frequent border rejections, as they are predominantly destined for direct household consumption, making them sensitive to safety standards (Gohin and Matthews, 2024). The final dataset is restricted to 193 pesticides regulated in both EU and Codex, affecting 117 HS6 commodities, between the years 2010 to 2023. To further refine the analysis, we classify pesticides by their level of hazardousness (i.e. extremely, highly, moderately, slightly and unlikely to present risks) based on WHO (2020). Then, we construct MRL stringency indices following Li and Beghin (2014), that average the distance between the MRLs adopted by the EU and Codex.

Traditionally, competitiveness has been measured via revealed comparative advantage (RCAs) indices as popularised by Balassa (1965). Several refinements have been proposed in the literature which are comprehensively evaluated by Stellian et al. (2024) on the grounds of

theoretical robustness and statistical properties, such as time stationarity, symmetry and ordinal ranking bias. Based on their performance, we choose three RCAs: revealed competitiveness (RC) (Danna-Buitrago and Stellian 2022); contribution to the trade balance (CTB) (Lafay, 1992); and gravity-based or regression-based RCA indexes (Z) (Costinot et al., 2012; Leromain and Orefice, 2014; French, 2017). A key difference between these indices is that, while the former two use both exports and imports in their computation, the latter, based on a gravity-type equation with bilateral trade, defines RCA based on exporter fixed effects that account for the underlying exporter's productivity. Finally, we run a panel fixed effect model where the RCA is regressed over the MRL stringency index, controlling for year and sector heterogeneity.

This paper contributes to several branches of the literature. First, we contribute with a novel constructed database of MRLs comparing European standards against the international Codex Alimentarius benchmark, categorized by the WHO level of hazardousness. Second, we bridge the gap between MRLs standards and competitiveness based on RCAs indicators. While recent studies have examined the impact of MRL harmonization on trade volumes, export and import prices, and quality (Shingal and Ehrich, 2024) the overall effect on long-term sectoral competitiveness remains understudied. By using improved RCA indexes, we provide a more robust measure of how regulatory stringency shifts a country's structural specialization. Third, we provide timely evidence for the European mirror clause debate.

The rest of the paper proceeds as follows. Section 2 presents the methodology including the construction of the different RCA indicators used and the econometric approach and data description. Section 3 presents the database construction and other data sources used. Section 4 presents the results while section 5 concludes discussing our main findings and offering policy recommendations

2. METHODS

2.1. Revealed Comparative Advantage Indexes

Although the original Balassa (1965) index is still widespread used, the trade literature provides a large set of candidates as Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA) indexes. Recently, Stellian et al. (2024) have evaluated an array of 33 RCA indexes classified into four categories: Balassa (B), Revealed Competitiveness (RC), Contribution to the Trade Balance (CTB) and gravity-based index (Z). Alternative regional composition and sectoral aggregations are considered in their definition and performance is evaluated on the basis of three main statistical properties: (i) stationarity or time stability of mean and variance which is necessary to track long-term trends

in competitiveness; (ii) symmetric shape with thin tails, such as the interval to reveal comparative (dis-)advantage and disadvantage is equal and preferably bounded; and (iii) minimisation of the ordinal ranking bias, to avoid situations where a better ranking position for a sector can be associated with a lower value of the index.

Based on the observed empirical performance, we choose the most common specification for RC, CTB and Z, as described below, and discard Balassa index because of the low performance on any of the above criteria. According to Stellian et al. (2024), the RC and Z indexes are more reliable than CTB in terms of ordinal ranking, which is particularly useful for economic policy purposes, and even if not as well positioned as the CTB index, still show good stability and shape properties. Between Z and RC, the latter seems to perform better in almost all the empirical distribution desirable properties. The regression-based Z index, on the other hand, is viewed as an interesting complement due to its more formal underpin in the Ricardian concept of comparative advantage, based on the intrinsic (ex-ante) productivity of each country in the production of a good, in contrast with RC and CTB where comparative advantage is revealed through the ex post realization of trade, blending not only exporters' productivity but also institutional, and importer and sector specific factors (Leromain and Orefice, 2014).

2.1.1. Revealed Competitive Index (RC)

The RC index used in this study, proposed by Danna-Buitrago and Stellian (2022), is grounded on the Balassa (1965) Index, and incorporates modifications by Vollrath (1991) as well as an additional transformation proposed by Dalum et al. (1998) to avoid the undefinition of the log-transformation.

Let J be a set of countries within which the revealed comparative advantage of a specific country i ($i=1, \dots, J$) is evaluated in sector k ($k=1, \dots, K$). Let X_{ikt} be the value of exports from exporter i in sector k and year t and M_{ikt} the value of imports. The RC index is:

$$RC_{ikt} = \left(\frac{BX_{ikt}-1}{BX_{ikt}+1} \right) - \left(\frac{BM_{ikt}-1}{BM_{ikt}+1} \right) \quad (1)$$

With

$$BX_{ikt} = \frac{X_{ikt}/\sum_{k=1}^K X_{ikt}}{\sum_{i=1}^J X_{ikt}/\sum_{i=1}^J \sum_{k=1}^K X_{ikt}} = \frac{X_{ikt}/X_{i.t}}{X_{.kt}/X_{..t}} \quad (2)$$

And

$$BM_{ikt} = \frac{M_{ikt}/\sum_{k=1}^K M_{ikt}}{\sum_{i=1}^J M_{ikt}/\sum_{i=1}^J \sum_{k=1}^K M_{ikt}} = \frac{M_{ikt}/M_{i.t}}{M_{.kt}/M_{..t}} \quad (3)$$

BX is the original Balassa Index of comparative advantage (Balassa, 1965), which relates the share of sector k in total exports of country i with respect to the equivalent share in a group of J countries, and as such, approximates a country's sectoral specialization. BX ranges from 0 to ∞ , with a neutral value of 1, so that a value greater than 1 means that country i has a comparative advantage in sector k and year t in comparison with the group. If no country exports k , then $\sum_i^N X_{ikt} = 0$, the index is not defined but a value of 1 is assigned given that no country has an advantage or disadvantage in sector k and year t .

To solve some of the limitations of the Balassa index 1, the RC index in (1) incorporates two modifications. First, a symmetric version of BX using an approximation of the log transformation (Dalum et al., 1998; Laursen, 2015): $\frac{(BX_{ikt}-1)}{(BX_{ikt}+1)}$ which ranges in the interval $[-1,1]$ and indicates a comparative advantage for values greater than 0. In comparison with the log of BX, this transformation avoids undefinition of the log when BX equals 0, as well as large negative values with very small values of BX (Danna-Buitrago and Stellian, 2022). And second, following Volrath (1991), both exports and imports are considered to capture comparative advantages in relation to both supply and demand. In this way, the relative imports advantage BM in (3) is subtracted from the relative exports advantage BX in (2): $BX_{ikt} - BM_{ikt}$, with positive values revealing a comparative advantage for country i in sector k and year t . $BM_{ikt} > 1$ reveals a comparative disadvantage in sector k , therefore, even if the Balassa index $BX > 1$, country i may not have a comparative advantage if $BM_{ikt} > BX_{ikt} > 1$. The RC index is bounded between -2 and 2, with a neutral value of 0.

2.1.2. Contribution to the Trade Balance Index (CTB)

The Contribution to Trade Balance Index (CTB) originates in Lafay (1992) and compares the trade balance of country i in sector k with a neutral or theoretical value, which is a weighted trade

¹ The empirical weaknesses of the Balassa index are well identified in the literature (see for instance Leromain and Orefice, 2014; Stellian and Danna-Buitrago, 2022; Danna-Buitrago and Stellian 2022). Besides time instability, asymmetry and ordinal ranking bias, explained in the text, the Balassa index presents: *i) small-country bias*: countries that export little tend to have, paradoxically, high values of the index: when $\sum_k^K X_{ikt} \rightarrow 0$, the numerator in (2) tends to infinite, and consequently, the index for i is larger the lesser its exports; *ii) lack of additivity*, making difficult the calculation of meaningful aggregated indexes, per country or per sector across a group of countries; and *iii) the Balassa index rules out comparative advantage based on differentiated qualities or varieties*, what would imply intra-industry trade.

² Strictly speaking, Volrath index excludes country i 's exports and imports in sector k from the summatory in both BX and BM indexes, but this removal could prevent the calculation of the index if a country is the sole exporter or importer of some product (Danna-Buitrago and Stellian, 2022).

balance of country i . Stellian and Danna-Buitrago (2022) use as weight the share of trade in sector k with respect to total trade in the area J ($w_{kt} = \frac{X_{kt} + M_{kt}}{X_{..t} + M_{..t}}$):³

$$CTB_{ikt} = \frac{(X_{ikt} - M_{ikt}) - w_{kt} \times (X_{i.t} - M_{i.t})}{X_{..t} + M_{..t}} \times 1000 \quad (4)$$

The difference between the sector k trade balance in country i and the theoretical value is then normalized by total trade in the region J ($X_{..t} + M_{..t}$). This normalization leads to extremely low values and Emlinger et al. (2015) suggest multiplying the index by 1000 for a better visualization. Values above (below) 0 imply that country i has a comparative (dis-) advantage in sector k .

2.1.3. Gravity based index (Z)

Following French (2017) who builds on Leromain and Orefice (2014) and Costinot et al. (2012) proposal, the gravity-based index (Z) is defined as the exporter-sector fixed effect (FE) estimated in a gravity equation where specific bilateral and importer-sector influences are captured by respective exporter-importer and importer-sector FE. The resulting exporter-sector fixed measures the country's fundamental comparative advantage. More specifically, Leromain and Orefice (2014) interpret it as reflecting the part of exports due to the intrinsic productivity level of a given sector k in a country i , given that all other determinants of export performance specific to each country-pair or importer, are fully controlled with their respective FEs.⁴

Our empirical application modifies Leromain and Orefice (2014) framework in two ways. First, rather than estimating a single equation for each year, the pool of years is included in the estimation, and the exporter-sector FE is replaced by exporter-sector-year FE δ_{ikt} . In this sense, our specification is closer to that of Stellian et al. (2024). Second, instead of using a log-linear OLS estimator, we adopt the latest developments in the gravity literature and use the Pseudo-Poisson Maximum Likelihood (PPML) estimator, also recommended by French (2017) in the current context, due to its superior consistency in the presence of heteroscedasticity (Santos Silva & Tenreyro, 2006), allowing as well to keep zero-trade values, characteristic of highly sectoral disaggregated data (French 2017). Thus, the regression to estimate is:

$$X_{ijkt} = \exp(\delta_{ij} + \delta_{ikt} + \delta_{jk} + \varepsilon_{ijkt}) \quad (5)$$

³ Lafay (1992) proposes as weight the share of trade in sector k ($X_{ikt} + M_{ikt}$) with respect to total trade of country i ($X_{i.t} + M_{i.t}$).

⁴ The exporter-sector fixed effects also capture factor endowments differences that are related to cross-country variation of productivity such as climate, infrastructure, historical specialization, and institutions that affect all producers in each country. Therefore, the exporter fixed effect is also able to capture productivity differences due to factor endowments and not only caused by differences in technology as a proper interpretation of the Ricardian model (see Leromain and Orefice, 2014 for more details).

Where X_{ijkt} is bilateral trade from i to j in sector k and year t ; and δ_{ij} is country pair, δ_{jk} importer-sector FE, and the Z index of revealed comparative advantage is obtained from the exporter-sector-year FE δ_{ikt} as:

$$Z_{ikt} = e^{\delta_{ikt}/\theta} \quad (6)$$

The value $\theta=6.53$ (as in Costinot et al., 2012; and Leromain and Orefice, 2014) represents the intra-industry heterogeneity (i.e. across varieties) of productivity.

Then, the index is normalized with respect to the group of available countries. In other words, comparative advantage of country i in sector k is compared with the world benchmark (Leromain and Orefice, 2014), which in our application corresponds to countries in region J :

$$ZN_{ikt} = \frac{Z_{ikt}/\overline{Z_{i,t}}}{\overline{Z_{\cdot kt}}/\overline{Z_{\cdot t}}} \quad (7)$$

Where $\overline{Z_{i,t}}$ is the average of Z_{ikt} across sectors k in country i ; $\overline{Z_{\cdot kt}}$ is the sector k average across all countries in the sample; and $\overline{Z_{\cdot t}}$ is the average across all sectors and countries. A value of ZN_{ik} larger than 1 indicates that country i has a comparative advantage in sector k .

2.2. MRL Stringency Index (score)

Maximum Residue Limits (MRLs) are widely used to regulate the application of pesticides in plant products. The World Health Organization (WHO) and Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) are the institutions competent in establishing by scientific methods the maximum levels that can be present in final food products without health hazard for humans, based on available scientific results. These levels are approved by the Codex Alimentarius Committee and are viewed as a benchmark for non-protectionist MRLs. Comparing the EU versus Codex at the product level provides information on how restrictive or liberal the EU is with respect to international standards.

We use the MRLs heterogeneity index proposed by Li and Beghin (2014) and used since then in several papers (e.g. Curzi et al. 2018; Santeramo et al. 2019; Fernandes et al. 2019). The MRL stringency index proposed by Li and Beghin (2014) compares the MRL for each pesticide p allowed in food sector k (defined at the product level as in our case at the HS6 level), by country i with the Codex international standard. Note that the higher this MRL, the less stringent is the regulation. Let $MRL_{EU,kt}^p$ be the maximum residue level authorized in the EU, of pesticide p in commodity k and year t ; and $MRL_{Codex,kt}^p$ the MRL recommended by Codex for the same commodity and pesticide. Using WHO (2022), the total number of pesticides P are classified into

m classes defined by hazard. Then P^m is the number of pesticides within each class m , and the corresponding score is:

$$Score_{EU,kt}^m = \frac{1}{P^m} \left(\sum_{p=1}^{P^m} \exp \left(\frac{MRL_{Codex,kt}^p - MRL_{EU,kt}^p}{MRL_{Codex,kt}^p} \right) \right) \quad (8)$$

The MRL stringency score varies in the positive range up to 2.72, being 1 the neutral value. If the EU sets MRLs on all pesticides affecting commodity k (in year t) equally stringent as those set by Codex, then the score is 1 (i.e. the numerator is 0). Values above 1 mean that averaging over all pesticides, the EU adopts stricter standards than Codex in that sector k , and values below 1 imply the EU being less strict than Codex. In the extreme, if the MRL adopted by the EU tend to zero, what de facto implies prohibition of pesticides affecting sector k , then the score will be 2.72. On the contrary, if the EU is systematically less strict than Codex, leading to large negative values in the numerator, then the score will tend to 0. The higher the score, the more stringent the EU's MRLs are in commodity k and year t , but only when the score is above 1, the EU is more stringent than Codex. The index is invariant to measurement units, as long as both the EU and Codex use the same units (e.g. parts per million, per billion); and by using the exponential, it is assumed that there is an increasing marginal difficulty of attaining stricter standards, in other words, the score increases more than proportionally with stringency levels beyond Codex (Li and Beghin, 2014).

2.3. Empirical specification

To empirically assess the relationship between the MRL stringency index in the EU compared to the international guidelines by the Codex Alimentarius and the EU competitiveness in agrifood trade, we estimate a panel regression of the form:

$$RCA_{ikt}^{noEU} = \beta \cdot Score_{kt} + \delta_t + \delta_k \quad (9)$$

Where $Score_{kt}$ is the MRL stringency index, δ_t and δ_k are year and sector fixed effects to control for time and sector heterogeneity. RCA_{ikt}^{noEU} is one of the three types of revealed comparative advantage indicators (RC, CTB and Z).^{5 6}, The superscript *noEU* means that the respective RCA index has been normalized with respect to non-EU countries. This normalization serves to have a better grasp of the EU competitiveness with respect to non-EU trade partners,

⁵ The RCA index varies by country, HS6 and year, while the MRL score index varies only by HS6 and year. Consequently, a regression on all data with sector and year FE is equivalent to a regression of the EU RCA average as dependent variable, or to a model that also includes country FE.

⁶ All the estimations are run in Stata 18 with the *reghdfe* command.

while seems coherent with the definition of the MRL score, defined as EU standards versus non-EU standards (proxied by Codex).⁷

In practice, the normalization of the RC index with respect to non-EU implies replacing the sectoral export share in the denominator of (2), $X_{kt}/X_{.t}$, and the sectoral import share in (3), $M_{kt}/M_{.t}$, by the respective shares of non-EU countries within the J area: $X_{noEUkt}/X_{noEU.t}$ and $M_{noEUkt}/M_{noEU.t}$, respectively.

The normalization of CTB with respect to non-EU countries, requires that the theoretical value (i.e. sectoral weighted trade balance) uses as weights the trade share of sector k in total trade by non-EU countries ($w_{kt} = \frac{X_{kt}+M_{kt}}{X_{noEU.t}+M_{noEU.t}}$) and the denominator in (4) being replaced by total trade of non-EU countries ($X_{noEU.t} + M_{noEU.t}$). By changing the weight, we guarantee that the additive property of the CTB index, that is, the sum of the CTB indexes of all k within a country i add to 0, is preserved.

Values above (below) 0 in both RC and CTB imply that country i in the EU has a comparative (dis-) advantage in sector k with respect to non-EU countries.

Finally, the Z index in equation (7) is normalized with respect to non-EU countries by replacing the global average values of Z in the denominator by those calculated over non-EU countries ($\overline{Z_{noEUkt}}/\overline{Z_{noEU.t}}$). Accordingly, a value larger than 1 indicates that country i in the EU has a comparative advantage in sector k in comparison with non-EU countries.

3. DATA

3.1. Maximum Residue Limits

EU MRL data comes from Eurostat (Eurostat, 2025a) and the EU active substance Database (Eurostat, 2025b) is checked for not approved or *de facto* banned substances in the EU. The MRLs set by Codex are downloaded from the WHO webpage (FAO-WHO, 2025).

Both Eurostat and Codex commodities lists are mapped to HS 6-digit. This leads to a common set of 117 HS6 products clearly identified in both datasets (see Table A.1). Our data covers HS6 products within vegetables (chapter HS2 07), fruits and nuts (chapter 08), coffee and spices (chapter 09), cereals (chapter 10), oil seeds (chapter 12) and cocoa (chapter 18).

⁷ The estimation results using non-normalized RCA indexes lead to identical conclusions in terms of direction and significance of influences of the stringency score, while the magnitudes are slightly smaller. These results are available upon request.

Most pesticides are named equal in both databases, but a thorough check is done using the Chemical Abstracts Service Registry (CAS) which is a unique numerical identifier assigned to a specific chemical substance.⁸ The result of the mapping of pesticides substances between Codex and Eurostat gives a total of 677 pesticides that appear in either or both databases. Table 1 describes the hazard categories established by WHO (2020) and shows the number of pesticides per hazard considered in the calculation of the MRL stringency score. WHO classification is based on scientific criteria to determine the toxicity (oral and dermal) of the technical compounds of pesticides. The categories, from more to less hazardous, are extremely hazardous (Ia), highly hazardous (Ib), moderately hazardous (II), slightly hazardous (III) and unlikely to present acute hazard in normal use (U). Two additional categories appear listed in WHO (2020)'s guidelines although, strictly speaking, do not pose any hazard: gaseous fumigants (FM) and obsolete (O). In our dataset, a common set of 193 pesticides is reported in both EU and Codex (in at least one commodity and year), from which, 190 can be classified according to hazard (185 excluding FM and O categories). The EU regulates on 293 additional pesticides in the selected HS6 sectors (see last column in Table 1), from which, 209 (193 excluding FM and O categories) can be classified according to hazard. MRL stringency scores are calculated for each of the five hazard categories from 'unlikely to present acute hazard' to 'extremely hazardous', and a total that includes all pesticides in the 7 categories listed.

Table 1. Categories of pesticides by hazard

Acronym	Description	Number of pesticides	
		EU & Codex	Only EU
Ia	Extremely hazardous	8	6
Ib	Highly hazardous	13	14
II	Moderately hazardous	69	62
III	Slightly hazardous	52	41
U	Unlikely to present acute hazard in normal use	43	62
FM	Fumigant, not classified	1	8
O	Obsolete	4	16
	Number of pesticides classified by hazard	190	209
	Total number of pesticides	193	293

Source: Own elaboration based on FAO-WHO (2025) and Eurostat (2025) for number of pesticides in the calculation of the MRL heterogeneity index, and WHO (2020) for the hazard classification of pesticides.

⁸ CAS numbers and pesticides names and compositions are checked in <https://www.cas.org>.

Eurostat provides full details on the current and past legislations establishing each pesticide MRLs, from which, the period of validity for each level of MRL can be obtained. Codex, on the other hand, includes a variable to indicate the year of adoption of each pesticide MRL value on each commodity currently in place, which ranges between 1991 and 2023, with 75% of observations starting in 2008 or later. The MRL for each pesticide-HS6 is then carried forward from the starting year of adoption. Using the time information on both datasets we build a panel for the period 2010-2023.

Finally, missing values for a combination pesticide-HS6-year exist in both, the EU and Codex data. Missing values in EU associated to pesticides for which no MRLs are required according to Annex IV of EC (2005), are preserved. In regulated pesticides, missing values in the EU are replaced by the default value of 0.01 parts per million (ppm or mg/kg), which is the minimum detectable level, as established by Article 18 of EC (2005). In our baseline model, we keep the missing values in Codex. In this way, the sample is restricted to those pesticide-HS6-year tiers where MRLs are reported by both Codex and Eurostat, thus differences between EU and Codex are not an artifact of the additional pesticides that the EU regulates.

3.2. Trade

Trade data in each of the 117 HS6 products and the period 2010-2023 used in the revealed comparative advantage indexes comes from UN ComTrade. Import values in current US dollars and c.i.f. (cost insurance freight included) are considered as import values are recognized to be more accurate (e.g. Larch, Shikher and Yotov, 2025).

The sample includes the 27 EU Member States plus United Kingdom (UK), and their 75 main trade partners which account for 95% of total trade (exports plus imports) in the 117 HS6 products and the period 2010-2023 (see Table 7 for the list of countries). In other words, the region J used in the RC and CTB indexes include 103 countries. Given the weight of intra-EU trade but also our main interest in computing competitiveness of the EU with respect to third countries, intra-EU trade is excluded from the computations of the three RCA indexes. The gravity-based Z index uses bilateral trade between the selected countries, excluding intra-EU trade, in the common set of 117 HS6 products and the 2010-2023 period.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Data descriptive analysis

Figure 1 shows that, for each category of pesticides defined according to its hazard, the EU sets more stringent MRL values than the Codex (values of the Score above 1). The median score is

1.41 when the score is calculated over the 193 pesticides in common. There is certain heterogeneity of MRL stringency levels, both within and across categories of pesticides. The within dispersion comes from alternative values of the MRL score across HS6 products and years, as indicated by the interquartile range (IQR) (i.e. the size of the box). Thus, dispersion across products and years is higher for the most hazardous pesticides, Ia and Ib, with IQR between around 1 and 2. Across hazard categories, we observe a higher dissimilarity between EU and Codex for more hazardous categories of pesticides (Ia and Ib) and slightly hazardous (III) with median scores higher than the remaining categories.

Figure 1. MRL score EU vs Codex by Hazard

Notes: MRL scores calculated over pesticides categorised as: extremely hazardous (Ia); highly hazardous (Ib); moderately hazardous (II); slightly hazardous (III); unlikely to present acute hazard (U). ‘All’ refers to the MRL score calculated over all 193 pesticides in common (see Table 1). The box represents the interquartile range (IQR), bounded by the 25th and 75th percentiles, while the horizontal line inside the box indicates the median. The whiskers extend to the most extreme observations within 1.5 times the IQR from the quartiles, and observations beyond this range are shown as outliers.

The correlation coefficient between RC and CTB is 0.46, and between RC and Z, 0.55 (in 2023), suggesting that there is substantial heterogeneity in the information captured by each of the RCA indexes. Whereas RC provide specialization changes through the lens of imports and exports relative to non-EU countries, CTB yields the trade balance contribution of a sector to strengthen the overall country trade balance. In instances where exports and imports shift in the same direction and at comparable rates, the net trade balance remains relatively stable. The Z index, on the other hand, captures the exporter–sector(-year) component which is attributable

to intrinsic productivity and fundamental strengths of the exporter (e.g. technology, factor endowments, climate, institutions), as bilateral trade frictions (e.g. geography) and importer-sector demand are controlled for. Nonetheless, there is a relatively high degree of consistency in signalling cases where revealed comparative advantages or disadvantages exist (values above and below the neutral value). Table 2 presents descriptive statistics for the three RCA indexes.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of the RCA indexes

	RC	CTB	Z
Mean	-0.246	0.000	1.000
Std. Dev.	0.774	0.222	0.494
Percentile 5	-1.534	-0.073	0.385
Median	-0.081	0.000	0.899
Percentile 95	1.306	0.081	1.982
Range (Min-Max)	(-1.997, 1.999)	(-9.023, 5.991)	(0.085, 4.167)

Notes: neutral values are 0 for RC and CTB and 1 for Z.

The heatmap in Figure 2 describes the RC variable across five EU regions and six HS2 sectors. EU countries (plus United Kingdom) are grouped into five regions according to their geographical and climatic proximity. The outcome groups are: Mediterranean (MEDIT), includes Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Malta, Spain and Portugal; Atlantic (ATLANT), includes Belgium, Denmark, France, United Kingdom, Ireland, Luxembourg and the Netherlands; Centre (CENTRE) includes Austria, Czechia, Germany, Hungary, Poland, Slovakia and Slovenia; Northern (NORTH) includes Estonia, Finland, Lithuania, Latvia and Sweden; and Balkan (BALKAN) includes Bulgaria, Croatia and Romania.

The figure shows a pronounced asymmetry in the data that spans from -2 to 2, with a median of -0.081, a mean of -0.246, and with 95% of observations in the range -1.53 – 1.30 (see Table 2). The data reveals a predominantly negative landscape, suggesting a systemic comparative disadvantage in the selected agricultural sectors for most regions, with few notable exceptions. First, cereals (HS2 10) emerge as the most competitive sector across the board probably reflecting favourable endowments (land- and capital-intensive sector), positive climate conditions, as well as historical support by the Common Agricultural Policy. Cereals is the only sector showing a positive RC in four out of five regions, with the Balkan region displaying the highest specialization (0.25), followed by the Centre (0.19) and North (0.16) regions. In contrast, cocoa (HS2 18) and fruits (HS2 08) exhibit the most pronounced comparative disadvantage in all regions, with the Centre, North and Atlantic regions showing the lowest performance. These deep red clusters suggest that the EU and these regions rely heavily on imports or have negligible

export shares in these specific commodities. The intensity of disadvantages in fruits is however significantly lower in the Mediterranean region. Vegetables (HS 07) is better positioned, with a predominance of comparative advantages in the Mediterranean and Atlantic regions, and with less intense disadvantages in comparison to other sectors. Figure 3 and Figure 4 in Appendix 2 replicate the heatmap for the CTB and Z indexes, respectively. Results show even more pronounced differences across sectors for these indexes maintaining the main conclusions that cereals present the largest RCAs and cacao the largest disadvantages. By region, Mediterranean and Atlantic also have the largest RCAs.

Figure 2. Heatmap of the distribution of Revealed Comparative Advantage (RC index) across sectors and regions

Notes: Values of RC are represented by a colour gradient, where shades of green indicate positive values (i.e. revealed comparative advantage) and shades of red denote negative values (i.e. revealed comparative disadvantage). The colour white corresponds to 0 or neutral value of RC. More intense green (red) colours indicate a higher frequency of positive (negative) RC values in the cell or HS2-region combination. Numerical values within each cell represent the mean RC observed for that specific HS2-region intersection. The HS2 chapters are vegetables (07), fruits (08), coffee and tea (09), cereals (10), oil seeds (12) and cocoa (18). The regions composition is: ATLANT (Belgium, Denmark, France, United Kingdom, Ireland, Luxembourg and the Netherlands), BALKAN (Bulgaria, Croatia and Romania), CENTRE (Austria, Czechia, Germany, Hungary, Poland, Slovakia and Slovenia), MEDIT (Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Malta, Spain and Portugal) and NORTH (Estonia, Finland, Lithuania, Latvia and Sweden).

4.2. Econometric analysis

4.2.1. Baseline results

The Results of the baseline model in (9) are presented in Table 3. Findings show a predominance of an inverse relationship between the MRL score and the RC index, statistically significant when

the score is calculated over all (common) pesticides and for three out of the five hazard categories. Thus, the more restrictive the EU regulations on MRLs are compared to the Codex guidelines, the more EU competitive position is weakened. This negative and significant relationship is observed for those pesticides classified as extremely (Ia), highly (Ib) and slightly (III) hazardous, with size effects that decrease from more (coefficients -0.116 and -0.047 for categories Ia and Ib, respectively) to less hazardous (coefficient -0.030 for category III, and 0 for U). Looking at the RC formula in (1), such decrease in RC may be due to a loss of the EU export market shares, weakening export specialization, a rise of import dependency, or a slower growth of EU exports than imports. Turning the coefficient -0.056 (column ALL, Table 3) into an elasticity, an increase in the stringency score of 1% is associated with a decrease in the RC index of 0.32% therefore deepening the EU difficulties in competing in the agrifood international markets.⁹

Table 3. Baseline results

RC	ALL	Ia	Ib	II	III	U
score	-0.056**	-0.116***	-0.047***	-0.009	-0.030***	0.001
	(0.026)	(0.031)	(0.015)	(0.023)	(0.010)	(0.014)
Observations	45,388	21,056	29,764	44,688	42,168	42,784
R-squared	0.331	0.358	0.334	0.333	0.329	0.334
CTB	ALL	Ia	Ib	II	III	U
score	0.000	-0.011***	-0.003	0.003	0.003	0.004
	(0.006)	(0.004)	(0.003)	(0.005)	(0.003)	(0.004)
Observations	45,388	21,056	29,764	44,688	42,168	42,784
R-squared	0.134	0.146	0.149	0.134	0.144	0.142
Z	ALL	Ia	Ib	II	III	U
score	-0.028	0.040*	0.028**	0.010	-0.026***	-0.014
	(0.020)	(0.022)	(0.011)	(0.018)	(0.009)	(0.012)
Observations	24,922	12,032	16,705	24,372	23,423	23,266
R-squared	0.275	0.300	0.288	0.274	0.266	0.272

Notes: All regressions include sector (k) and year (t) fixed effects. ***, ** and * stand for significance at 1, 5 and 10%, respectively. Robust standard errors in parentheses, clustered by country and sector (ik). Each column reports results for MRL scores calculated over pesticides categorised as: extremely hazardous (Ia); highly hazardous (Ib); moderately hazardous (II); slightly hazardous (III); unlikely to present acute hazard (U). The column ALL refers to the MRL score calculated over all common pesticides (see Table 1). RC stands

⁹ The elasticity is calculated as: $\beta \cdot \frac{\overline{Score}}{|\overline{RC}|}$ where \overline{Score} and \overline{RC} stand for the average values of Score and RC, respectively (1.453 and -0.246).

for Relative Competitiveness Index; CTB is Contribution to Trade Balance Index; and Z is the gravity-based Comparative Advantage index, as described in equations (1), (4) and (7), respectively.

For CTB indexes, the negative relationship is significant only for highly hazardous pesticides. As presented in the methodological section and in section 5.1. the CTB index may remain quite stable under comparable change rates of both imports and exports that neutralize changes in the trade balance, resulting in non-significant effects. The emergence of significant effects solely for highly hazardous pesticides suggests that these offsetting mechanisms attenuate when regulatory stringency is sufficiently high (note that the MRL score exhibits the largest divergence between the EU and Codex in median and average, Figure 1).

Regarding the Z index (last panel in Table 3), a negative and significant relationship (as with RC) is observed for slightly hazardous pesticides, and a negative albeit non-significant for All pesticides. A different pattern emerges, though, for extremely and highly hazardous pesticides, as a positive and significant relationship is observed. This suggests that sectors with stronger underlying productivity or more favourable cost structures are better able to absorb the increase in MRL policy compliance costs. This also supports Chen et al. (2024) findings that MRL standards facilitate exports conditional on exporting (intensive margin). This might also underlie differences in consumers' perceived health risks across products. For goods associated with higher potential health hazards, consumers (and importers) may exhibit a higher willingness to pay for stricter standards, leading to quality upgrading and sourcing from high-standard countries. In contrast, for less risky products, price considerations may dominate, resulting in sourcing from lower-cost, lower-standard suppliers

In summary, the findings suggest that MRL stringency reshapes comparative advantage not by uniformly reducing trade, but by altering relative costs and reallocating export activity toward producers with stronger underlying productivity (Shingal and Ehrich, (2024); Fontagné et al. 2015; Disdier et al. 2023). This helps reconcile the apparent tension between cost-increasing and demand- or protection-enhancing effects, showing that both can coexist and jointly determine observed trade patterns.

4.2.2. Results by sector and region

Next, we investigate if the relationships observed in Table 3 are homogeneous across sectors and countries. For this purpose, the MRL stringency score is interacted with HS2 chapters (Table 4) and with geographical regions, as defined in Section 5.1 (Table 5).

Table 4 reveals that the relationship between MRL restrictiveness and RCA is heterogeneous across HS2 chapters. According to the RC index, the inverse relationship is especially significant for vegetables (HS2 07) and fruits (HS2 08), and to a lesser extent, for coffee and tea (HS2 09) and, as in the baseline model, especially relevant for extremely and highly hazardous pesticides. The EU has a clear comparative disadvantage in fruits (see Figure 2), which explains the high sensitiveness of the RC index to increasing levels of EU MRL stringency (the coefficients on Ia and II pesticides are -0.427 and -0.139, the largest, in absolute terms, across the board). For cereals (HS2 10) and oil seeds (HS2 12) there is a mixture of effects, both positive and negative, contingent upon the pesticides hazard. Thus, a deviation from international standards on more hazardous pesticides damages EU competitiveness, as observed in the general trend (Table 3) and the remaining sectors (Table 4), while such deviation in less hazardous pesticides benefits EU competitiveness. This beneficial effect, not found in other sectors, might be related to the fact that both cereals and oilseeds enjoy higher levels of RCA (see Figure 2). Finally, no significant effects are observed in cacao (HS2 18). Results of the CTB index agree partially with those of the RC index, supporting the pervasiveness of negative impacts in vegetables, the lack of impact in cacao, as well as the positive effect observed for the stringency score of moderately hazardous pesticides in cereals. As per fruits and oilseeds, weaker evidence is found with the CTB index. In contrast with RC results, however, a positive and significant effect is observed for category III in fruits and coffee & tea.

Turning to the Z index, the positive effect observed in the baseline model (Table 3) for extremely and highly hazardous pesticides, is manifested in cereals and oilseeds, and vegetables and fruits, respectively, as stringent regulations favour EU most productive exporters, while the negative sign for slightly hazardous (III) in the overall model, can be pinpointed to fruits, coffee & tea and cereals.

Table 4. Estimation results with sector (HS2) interactions

RC	ALL	Ia	Ib	II	III	U
score x 07	-0.190*** (0.053)	-0.085** (0.035)	-0.029 (0.020)	-0.067 (0.046)	-0.045*** (0.017)	-0.051** (0.022)
score x 08	-0.079** (0.036)	-0.427*** (0.152)	-0.048* (0.027)	-0.139*** (0.038)	-0.024 (0.021)	0.032 (0.022)
score x 09	-0.084 (0.061)	-0.086 (0.068)	-0.148** (0.060)	0.003 (0.040)	-0.060*** (0.022)	0.012 (0.040)
score x 10	0.052 (0.067)	-0.266* (0.142)	0.044 (0.032)	0.135* (0.071)	-0.014 (0.022)	0.047 (0.071)
score x 12	0.135* (0.070)	0.043 (0.248)	-0.159*** (0.056)	0.198*** (0.068)	0.024 (0.041)	0.016 (0.029)
score x 18	-0.054 (0.124)			-0.062 (0.073)		0.000 (0.000)
Obs	45,388	21,056	29,764	44,688	42,168	42,784
R-squared	0.331	0.359	0.335	0.334	0.329	0.334
CTB	ALL	Ia	Ib	II	III	U
score x 07	-0.011*** (0.003)	-0.019*** (0.006)	-0.002 (0.002)	-0.000 (0.003)	-0.004*** (0.001)	-0.003* (0.002)
score x 08	0.013 (0.014)	0.000 (0.023)	-0.000 (0.003)	0.014 (0.013)	0.009** (0.005)	-0.002 (0.006)
score x 09	0.006 (0.008)	0.025 (0.018)	-0.011** (0.005)	-0.005 (0.004)	0.027* (0.015)	0.058** (0.029)
score x 10	0.024 (0.020)	-0.172 (0.118)	0.004 (0.017)	0.045** (0.019)	-0.005 (0.006)	-0.024 (0.015)
score x 12	-0.002 (0.006)	-0.010 (0.012)	-0.018*** (0.007)	0.001 (0.005)	-0.002 (0.004)	0.002 (0.001)
score x 18	-0.154 (0.134)			-0.126 (0.085)		0.000 (0.000)
Obs	45,388	21,056	29,764	44,688	42,168	42,784
R-squared	0.134	0.146	0.150	0.134	0.144	0.142
Z	ALL	Ia	Ib	II	III	U
score x 07	-0.028 (0.039)	0.037 (0.028)	0.029* (0.016)	0.091** (0.036)	-0.007 (0.015)	-0.034 (0.023)
score x 08	-0.066** (0.033)	-0.099 (0.132)	0.037** (0.017)	-0.125*** (0.036)	-0.044** (0.019)	0.026 (0.019)
score x 09	0.020 (0.039)	0.005 (0.046)	-0.046 (0.037)	0.041 (0.027)	-0.035** (0.017)	-0.022 (0.032)
score x 10	-0.091 (0.066)	0.346** (0.173)	0.049 (0.041)	0.009 (0.071)	-0.049* (0.027)	-0.086 (0.076)
score x 12	0.031 (0.047)	0.227* (0.134)	0.011 (0.033)	0.067 (0.047)	-0.014 (0.026)	-0.016 (0.021)
score x 18	-0.228 (0.142)			-0.163 (0.109)		0.000 (0.000)
Obs	24,922	12,032	16,705	24,372	23,423	23,266
R-squared	0.275	0.300	0.288	0.274	0.266	0.272

Notes: All regressions include sector (k) and year (t) fixed effects. ***, ** and * stand for significance at 1, 5 and 10%, respectively. Robust standard errors in parentheses, clustered by country and sector (ik). HS2 sectors are: 07 Vegetables; 08 Fruits; 09 Coffee and tea; 10 Cereals; 12 Oilseeds; 18 Cocoa. Each column reports results for MRL scores calculated over pesticides categorised as: extremely hazardous (Ia); highly hazardous (Ib); moderately hazardous (II); slightly hazardous (III); unlikely to present acute hazard (U). The column ALL refers to the MRL score calculated over all pesticides (see Table 1).

Beyond sectoral dynamics, the results in Table 5 reveal substantial regional heterogeneity in patterns of competitiveness. The RC index shows a pervasiveness of significant and negative associations between the stringency MRL score and competitiveness in the Balkan, Centre and North regions, while the Mediterranean area, characterized by higher levels of RCA (Figure 2) shows positive and significant relationships in five out of the six hazard categories. The Mediterranean region stands out for its relative specialisation in horticulture products particularly vegetables and fruits to a lesser extent even when it remains as a net importer. As a result, regions with higher RCA might benefit from more stringent pesticides regulations, which can embed quality signals in their exports allowing exporters to surpass the higher costs of entry. The Atlantic area is the second region with higher levels of RCA after the Mediterranean region, and the RC index only shows a negative and significant association of pesticide stringency and RCA on extremely (1a) and highly hazardous pesticides (1b).

As in previous analysis, the CTB index shows predominantly a null effect, with some negative and significant effects scattered across the board. When only the country's intrinsic productivity is considered in Z, we observe that the MRL effects are even positive, showing that the EU exports competitiveness might be favoured by the higher quality of food products due to more stringent standards. Therefore, and similarly to our observation when segmenting by HS2 chapter, we find that the relationship between MRL restrictiveness and RCA is weaker (or even positive) in those regions that enjoy higher competitive advantage even turning to positive effects in the Mediterranean area. While the Balkan, Centre and North regions which have lower levels of RCA show large negative effects bearing a disproportionate share of the competitiveness losses.

Table 5. Estimation results with region interactions

RC	ALL	Ia	Ib	II	III	U
score x ATLANT	-0.038 (0.029)	-0.128*** (0.034)	-0.059*** (0.020)	0.004 (0.026)	-0.012 (0.015)	0.019 (0.018)
score x BALKAN	-0.098*** (0.032)	-0.151*** (0.041)	-0.102*** (0.026)	-0.056* (0.030)	-0.064*** (0.020)	-0.040* (0.024)
score x CENTRE	-0.114*** (0.028)	-0.150*** (0.033)	-0.086*** (0.019)	-0.068*** (0.025)	-0.082*** (0.014)	-0.058*** (0.017)
score x MEDIT	0.061** (0.029)	-0.006 (0.036)	0.091*** (0.022)	0.115*** (0.027)	0.074*** (0.016)	0.119*** (0.020)
score x NORTH	-0.113*** (0.028)	-0.162*** (0.036)	-0.109*** (0.020)	-0.066** (0.026)	-0.086*** (0.015)	-0.057*** (0.019)
Observations	45,388	21,056	29,764	44,688	42,168	42,784
R-squared	0.348	0.373	0.358	0.351	0.345	0.351
CTB	ALL	Ia	Ib	II	III	U
score x ATLANT	0.001 (0.008)	-0.005 (0.008)	-0.002 (0.005)	0.003 (0.007)	0.006 (0.005)	0.005 (0.005)
score x BALKAN	-0.001 (0.006)	-0.012 (0.007)	-0.009* (0.005)	0.001 (0.005)	0.002 (0.004)	0.002 (0.005)
score x CENTRE	0.001 (0.006)	-0.010 (0.007)	0.000 (0.004)	0.004 (0.007)	0.002 (0.003)	0.004 (0.004)
score x MEDIT	0.001 (0.006)	-0.014* (0.008)	0.000 (0.005)	0.004 (0.005)	0.002 (0.004)	0.004 (0.005)
score x NORTH	-0.001 (0.006)	-0.014** (0.006)	-0.008* (0.004)	0.002 (0.005)	0.003 (0.004)	0.002 (0.005)
Observations	45,388	21,056	29,764	44,688	42,168	42,784
R-squared	0.134	0.147	0.150	0.134	0.144	0.142
Z	ALL	Ia	Ib	II	III	U
score x ATLANT	-0.014 (0.022)	0.046** (0.023)	0.033** (0.014)	0.023 (0.020)	-0.018 (0.011)	0.001 (0.014)
score x BALKAN	-0.060** (0.027)	0.019 (0.031)	0.000 (0.024)	-0.022 (0.027)	-0.050*** (0.019)	-0.044** (0.022)
score x CENTRE	-0.039* (0.022)	0.017 (0.024)	0.004 (0.015)	-0.004 (0.020)	-0.035*** (0.012)	-0.025* (0.014)
score x MEDIT	-0.005 (0.023)	0.065** (0.027)	0.072*** (0.017)	0.042** (0.021)	-0.009 (0.013)	0.005 (0.016)
score x NORTH	-0.065*** (0.024)	0.031 (0.032)	-0.015 (0.021)	-0.028 (0.023)	-0.056*** (0.015)	-0.056*** (0.018)
Observations	24,922	12,032	16,705	24,372	23,423	23,266
R-squared	0.279	0.303	0.297	0.279	0.269	0.276

Notes: All regressions include sector (k) and year (t) fixed effects. ***, ** and * stand for significance at 1, 5 and 10%, respectively. Robust standard errors in parentheses, clustered by country and sector (ik). The regions composition is: ATLANT (Belgium, Denmark, France, United Kingdom, Ireland, Luxembourg and the Netherlands), BALKAN (Bulgaria, Croatia and Romania), CENTRE (Austria, Czechia, Germany, Hungary, Poland, Slovakia and Slovenia), MEDIT (Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Malta, Spain and Portugal) and NORTH (Estonia, Finland, Lithuania, Latvia and Sweden).. Each column reports results for MRL scores calculated over pesticides categorised as: extremely hazardous (Ia); highly hazardous (Ib); moderately hazardous (II); slightly hazardous (III); unlikely to present acute hazard (U). The column ALL refers to the MRL score calculated over all pesticides (see Table 1).

5. DISCUSSION AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

This paper investigates the relationship between pesticide regulation measured through maximum residue levels (MRLs) and agri-food competitiveness in the European Union. We construct a novel dataset on EU and Codex MRLs including stringency indicators and established revealed comparative advantage indicators (RC, CTB, and Z). Results are heterogeneous but we find an overall negative association for MRLs stringency and competitiveness, especially for extremely- and highly- hazardous pesticides. However, the positive effects on the country's intrinsic productivity level suggest that more efficient producers can expand their market shares in third countries. Particularly, disaggregated analysis reveals significant sectoral and geographic heterogeneity. Fruit and vegetable sectors experience the most substantial losses in market specialization contrary to cereals. Regionally, producers in the Balkans, Central- and Northern-Europe bear a disproportionate share of these competitiveness losses.

The findings suggest that the stricter pesticide regulations in place in the EU play a central and complex role in shaping EU agri-food competitiveness. Within a Ricardian context, those regions or sectors with higher comparative advantage are the ones less affected by MRL stringency and they can even benefit from the protection MRLs provide improving their performance in export markets. At the firm level, these findings suggest that MRLs lead to reallocations in export activity toward more efficient producers consistent with Fernandes et al. (2019) and Disdier et al. (2023). This evidence helps to disentangle whether standards act as trade barriers or catalysts by showing that these effects can coexist and shape trade patterns based on productivity and competitiveness levels. Producers with higher comparative advantage will bear the cost increasing part but reap the benefits from the demand enhancing and import protection effects while those firms with lower productivity levels will be harmed by the cost increasing effects and might be forced to compete only in the domestic market. Competitiveness is therefore reshaped through selection mechanisms rather than uniformly reduced.

From a policy perspective, the results provide timely insights into the ongoing debate on mirror clauses and regulatory convergence. The evidence suggests that the EU's regulatory stringency relative to Codex is leading to an erosion of competitiveness, particularly in sectors and regions with weaker structural advantages. In this context, mirroring import standards with domestic regulations could help mitigate competitive imbalances, especially for highly hazardous pesticides where regulatory gaps are largest and where RCA sensitiveness is also larger. However, the heterogeneous effects by sector, region and hazard level also caution against adopting mirror clauses as a one-size-fits-all approach. Instead, policy interventions should be targeted and

differentiated, focusing on those sectors and substances where regulatory asymmetries generate the largest distortions (i.e. for extremely and highly hazardous substances).

Finally, the paper opens avenues for future research. First, further work could explore firm-level dynamics to test and understand the mechanisms underlying the observed selection effects. Second, extending the MRL stringency score calculations to a larger set of countries would allow for a more detailed assessment of how regulatory differences affect trade patterns across partners. Third, evaluating the interaction between CAP support and regulatory stringency could provide additional insights into the role of policy in shaping competitiveness outcomes.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This document was produced under the terms and conditions of Grant Agreement No. 101060075 for the European Commission. It does not necessarily reflect the view of the European Union and in no way anticipates the Commission's future policy in this area.

7. REFERENCES

- Balassa, B. (1965). Trade liberalisation and "revealed" comparative advantage 1. The manchester school, 33(2), 99-123. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9957.1965.tb00050.x>
- Barreiro-Hurle, J., Bogonos, M., Himics, M., Hristov, J., Pérez-Domiguez, I., Sahoo, A., Salputra, G., Weiss, F., Baldoni, E., Elleby, C. Modelling environmental and climate ambition in the agricultural sector with the CAPRI model. Exploring the potential effects of selected Farm to Fork and Biodiversity strategies targets in the framework of the 2030 Climate targets and the post 2020 Common Agricultural Policy, EUR 30317 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2021, ISBN 978-92-76-20889-1, doi:10.2760/98160, JRC121368.).
- Beckman, J., M. Ivanic, J. Jelliffe, F. Baquedano, and S. Scott. 2020. Economic and Food Security Impacts of Agricultural Input Reduction under the European Union Green Deal's Farm to Fork and Biodiversity Strategies.
- Chen, B., Chen, Y., & Zhang, S. (2024). The effect of maximum residue limit standards on China's agri-food exports: A health perspective. *Review of International Economics*, 32(4), 1698-1725. <https://doi.org/10.1111/roie.12752>
- Costinot, A., Donaldson, D., Komunjer, I. (2012). What goods do countries trade? A quantitative exploration of Ricardo's ideas. *Review of Economic Studies* 79: 581-608. <https://doi.org/10.1093/restud/rdr033>
- Curzi, D., Luarasi, M., Raimondi, V., & Olper, A. (2018). The (lack of) international harmonization of EU standards: import and export effects in developed versus developing countries. *Applied Economics Letters*, 25(21), 1552-1556. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504851.2018.1430327>
- Danna-Buitrago, J.P. and Stellian, R. (2022). A new class of revealed comparative advantage indexes. *Open Economies Review* 33: 477-503. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11079-021-09636-4>

- Disdier, A. C., Gaigné, C., & Herghelegiu, C. (2023). Do standards improve the quality of traded products? *Canadian Journal of Economics/Revue canadienne d'économique*, 56(4), 1238-1290. <https://doi.org/10.1111/caje.12678>
- Droguè, S. and Demaria, F. (2012). Pesticide residues and trade, the apple of discord? *Food Policy* 37, 641-649. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2012.06.007>
- EC (2005). Regulation (EC) No 396/2005 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 February 2005 on maximum residue levels of pesticides in or on food and feed of plant and animal origin and amending Council Directive 91/414/EEC (OJ L 70, 16.3.2005, p.1)
- Emlinger, C., Guimbard, H. & Saint Vaulry, A. (2015). CEPII country profiles: indicators, databases and classifications. *Panorama du CEPII* N° 2015-M-01, June.
- Eurostat (2025a). [data] <https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/pesticides/eu-pesticides-database/start/screen/mrls> [accessed February 2025]
- Eurostat (2025b). [data] <https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/pesticides/eu-pesticides-database/start/screen/active-substances> [accessed February 2025]
- FAO-WHO (2025). [Data] <https://www.fao.org/fao-who-codexalimentarius/codex-texts/dbs/pestres/en/> [accessed March 2025]
- FAO-WHO (2025). [Data] <https://www.fao.org/fao-who-codexalimentarius/codex-texts/dbs/pestres/commodities/en/> [accessed April 2025].
- Fernandes, A. M., Ferro, E., & Wilson, J. S. (2019). Product standards and firms' export decisions. *The World Bank Economic Review*, 33(2), 353-374. <https://doi.org/10.1093/wber/lhw071>
- Ferro, E., Otsuki, T., & Wilson, J. S. (2015). The effect of product standards on agricultural exports. *Food Policy*, 50, 68-79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2014.10.016>
- Fiankor, D. D. D., Curzi, D., & Olper, A. (2021). Trade, price and quality upgrading effects of agri-food standards. *European Review of Agricultural Economics*, 48(4), 835-877.
- Fontagné, L., Orefice, G., Piermartini, R., & Rocha, N. (2015). Product standards and margins of trade: Firm-level evidence. *Journal of international economics*, 97(1), 29-44. <https://doi.org.unizar.idm.oclc.org/10.1016/j.jinteco.2015.04.008>
- French, S. (2017). Revealed comparative advantage: What is it good for? *Journal of International Economics*, 106, 83-103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinteco.2017.02.002>
- Grant, J.H. and S. Arita. 2016 Forthcoming. Revealed Concerns: A New Look at the Impact of Non-Tariff Measures on Agri-Food Trade, Commissioned Paper, International Agricultural Trade Research Consortium (IATRC), June 2016.

- Gohin, A., & Matthews, A. (2024). Adding mirror clauses within the European Green Deal: Hype or hope? *Applied Economic Perspectives and Policy*, 46(3), 1103-1126. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aapp.13434>
- Lafay, G. (1992). The measurement of revealed comparative advantages. In M.G. Agenais & P.-A. Muet (Eds.): *International trade modelling* (pp.209-234). Chapman & Hall.
- Larch, M., Shikher, S., & Yotov, Y. V. (2025). Estimating gravity equations: Theory implications, econometric developments, and practical recommendations. *Review of international economics*, 33(5), 1066-1092. <https://doi.org/10.1111/roie.12789>
- Laursen, K. (2015). Revealed comparative advantage and the alternatives as measures of international specialization. *Eurasian Business Review* 5(1): 99-115. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40821-015-0017-1>
- Leromain, E. and Orefice, G. (2014). New revealed comparative advantage index: Dataset and empirical distribution. *International Economics* 139: 48-70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inteco.2014.03.003>.
- Li, Y. and Beghin, J.C. (2014). Protectionism indices for non-tariff measures: An application to maximum residue levels. *Food Policy* 45: 57-68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2013.12.005>.
- Maertens, M. and Swinnen, J. F. M. (2009). Trade, standards, and poverty: evidence from Senegal. *World Development* 37(1), 161–178
- Melitz, M. J. (2003). The impact of trade on intra-industry reallocations and aggregate industry productivity. *Econometrica*, 71(6), 1695-1725. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-0262.00467>
- Olper, A., Curzi, D. and Pacca, L. (2014). Do Food Standards affect the Quality of EU Imports? *Economics Letters* 122, 233-237.
- Santeramo, F.G. and Lamonaca, E. (2019), The Effects of Non-tariff Measures on Agri-food Trade: A Review and Meta-analysis of Empirical Evidence. *J Agric Econ*, 70: 595-617. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1477-9552.12316>
- Santos Silva, J., & Tenreyro, S. (2006). The log of gravity. *The Review of Economics and statistics*, 641-658. DOI:10.1162/rest.88.4.641
- Shingal, A., & Ehrich, M. (2024). The EU's pesticides MRLs harmonization: Effect on trade, prices and quality. *Food Policy*, 125, 102634. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2024.102634>
- Stellian, R. and Danna-Buitrago, P. (2022). Which revealed comparative advantage index to choose? Theoretical and empirical considerations. *CEPAL Review* N°138.

- Stellian, R., Ojeda-Joya, J.N. and Danna-Buitrago, J.P. (2024). Thime stationarity, shape and ordinal ranking bias of RCA indexes: a new set of measures. *Review of World Economics* 160: 675-711. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10290-023-00512-6>.
- Vollrath, T. L. (1991). A theoretical evaluation of alternative trade intensity measures of revealed comparative advantage. *Weltwirtschaftliches Archiv*, 127, 265–280. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02707986>
- WHO (2020). *The WHO Recommended Classification of Pesticides by Hazard and Guidelines to Classification*, 2019 edition. Geneva: World Health Organization; CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240005662>

APPENDIX 1: THE SAMPLE

Table 6. List of products: HS6 codes and HS4 Description

Vegetables		HS6					Coffee and Spices		HS6			
0701	Potatoes	070110	070190				0901	Coffee	090111	090112	090121	090122
0702	Tomatoes	070200					0902	Tea	090210	090220	090230	090240
0703	Onions, Shallots and Garlic	070310	070320	070390			0904	Pepper and Chilies	090411	090412		
0704	Cabbages, Cauliflowers and Kale	070410	070420	070490			0908	Nutmeg and Cardamom	090830			
0705	Lettuce and Chicory	070511	070519	070521			0909	Spice Seeds	090920	090930	090950	
0706	Carrots, Turnips and Salad Beetroot	070610	070690				0910	Ginger and Other Spices	091010	091030	091099	
0707	Cucumbers and Gherkins	070700					Cereals		HS6			
0708	Leguminous Vegetables (peas, beans, etc.)	070810	070820				1001	Wheat	100110	100190		
0709	Other Vegetables	070920	070930	070940	070951	070959	1002	Rye	100200			
	(asparagus, mushrooms, peppers, etc.)	070960	070970	070990			1003	Barley	100300			
0711	Provisionally Preserved Vegetables	071120					1004	Oats	100400			
0713	Dried Leguminous Vegetables (pulses)	071310	071332	071333	071339	071340	1005	Maize (Corn)	100510	100590		
		071390					1006	Rice	100610	100620	100630	100640
0714	Cassava, Sweet Potatoes and similar roots	071410	071420				1007	Sorghum	100700			

							1008	Buckwheat and Millets	100810	100820		
Fruits and Nuts		HS6						Oil Seeds and Grains	HS6			
0801	Coconuts, Brazil Nuts, and Cashew Nuts	080131	080132				1202	Peanuts	120210	120220		
0802	Other Nuts	080211	080212	080221	080222	080231	1204	Linseed	120400			
	(almonds, hazelnuts, walnuts, etc.)	080232	080250	080260	080290		1205	Rape and Colza Seed	120590			
0803	Bananas and Plantains	080300				080450	1206	Sunflower Seeds	120600			
0804	Dates, Figs, Pineapples, Avocados, and Guavas	080410	080420	080430	080440		1207	Other Oils Seeds	120720	120750	120791	120799
0805	Citrus Fruit	080510	080520	080540	080550		1210	Hop Cones	121010	121020		
0806	Grapes	080610					1211	Medicinal Plants	121120			
0807	Melons and Papayas	080711	080719	080720			1212	Locust Beans and Sugar Beet	121291	121299		
0808	Apples, Pears, and Quinces	080810	080820									
0809	Apricots, Cherries, Peaches, and Plums	080910	080920	080930	080940		Cocoa					
0810	Other Fruit (berries, kiwi, durian, etc.)	081010	081020	081040	081050		1801	Cocoa Beans	180100			

Table 7. List of countries in the sample

Non-EU countries: Angola, Albania, United Arab Emirates, Argentina, Australia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Belarus, Brazil, Canada, Switzerland, Chile, China, Côte d'Ivoire, Cameroon, Colombia, Costa Rica, Dominican Republic, Algeria, Ecuador, Egypt, Ethiopia, Georgia, Ghana, Guatemala, Hong Kong, Honduras, Indonesia, India, Iran, Iceland, Israel, Jordan, Japan, Kazakhstan, Kenya, Cambodia, South Korea, Kuwait, Lebanon, Sri Lanka, Morocco, Moldova, Mexico, North Macedonia, Myanmar, Mauritania, Malaysia, Nigeria, Nicaragua, Norway, New Zealand, Pakistan, Panama, Peru, Philippines, Papua New Guinea, Qatar, Russia, Saudi Arabia, Sudan, Senegal, Singapore, El Salvador, Serbia, Thailand, Tunisia, Turkey, Uganda, Ukraine, Uruguay, United States, Vietnam, Yemen, South Africa, Zimbabwe.

EU countries: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, United Kingdom is included as an additional country in the EU group for the computation of the RCA indexes as it was an EU member state for most of the sample period (up to 2021).

APPENDIX 2: ADDITIONAL RESULTS

Figure 3. Heatmap of the distribution of Revealed Comparative Advantage (CTB variable) across sectors and regions

Notes: To ease visualisation, CTB is multiplied by 10,000. Values of CTB are represented by a colour gradient, where shades of green indicate values greater than 0 (i.e. revealed comparative advantage) and shades of red denote values lower than 0 (i.e. revealed comparative disadvantage). The colour white corresponds to 0 or neutral value of CTB. More intense green (red) colours indicate a higher frequency of values greater than zero (lower than zero). Numerical values within each cell represent the mean CTB observed for that specific HS2-region intersection.

Figure 4. Heatmap of the distribution of Revealed Comparative Advantage (Z variable) across sectors and regions

Notes: Values of Z are represented by a colour gradient, where shades of green indicate values greater than 1 (i.e. revealed comparative advantage) and shades of red denote values lower than 1 (i.e. revealed comparative disadvantage). The colour white corresponds to 1 or neutral value of Z. More intense green (red) colours indicate a higher frequency of values greater than one (lower than one). Numerical values within each cell represent the mean Z observed for that specific HS2-region intersection.

www.brightspace-project.eu
www.brightspace-horizon.eu

